

The potential role of Artificial Intelligence in public health: A scoping review

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Table of Contents

<i>The potential role of Artificial Intelligence in public health: A scoping review</i>	1
1. Background	4
2. Review Aim	6
3. Methods	6
3.1. Patient and Public Involvement (PPI)	6
3.2. Approach to Searching and Data Sources	7
3.3. Eligibility Criteria	8
3.4. Study Screening Methods	8
3.5. Software	9
3.6. Quality Appraisal	9
3.7. Number of Reviewers	9
3.8. Data Extraction and Coding	9
3.9. Synthesis	10
3.10. Synthesis Output	10
3.11. Certainty of Evidence	11
4. Ethics	11
5. Discussion	11
References	12
Table 1. Stakeholder Engagement in Review Process	14
Table 2: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria	15
Supplement A: Search Strategy (Medline)	16

1. Background

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a broad field encompassing various techniques, including machine learning, natural language processing, and computer vision (1). AI, which refers to algorithms integrated into systems and tools, learns from data to be able to perform automated tasks without explicit human programming (2-4).

AI is particularly useful for tasks requiring pattern recognition, prediction, and data analysis (5). In healthcare, for instance, AI applications have been used to enhance image analysis, streamline operations, enable personalized and predictive healthcare, and support clinical decision-making (6). In public health, AI has been used for spatial modelling, risk prediction, misinformation control, public health surveillance, disease forecasting, and epidemic and pandemic modelling (5). Additionally, conversational AI interventions have been used to support smoking cessation (7) and reducing alcohol intake (8), and AI-assisted apps have been used to improve exercise technique (9). Other uses of AI in public health remain hypothesised but un- or under-explored in practice, for instance in public communication (10).

The COVID-19 pandemic, in particular, highlighted both the challenges and opportunities for using AI in public health. The scale and severity of the pandemic underscored the need for more efficient and effective interventions, and AI was used for disease surveillance, contact tracing, combating misinformation, predicting transmission patterns, and forecasting disease spread (5).

While the theoretical groundwork for machine learning and deep learning was laid in the 1980s, recent advancements in computing power and the development of large language models like OpenAI's ChatGPT and Google's Gemini have sparked renewed interest in AI. These models, with more user-friendly interfaces and general-purpose applications, offer the potential to help tackle a wide range of problems (11).

However, even if AI-assisted interventions in public health are shown to be effective, there are nonetheless barriers to the adoption of AI. These include public trust, health equity, ethical considerations, data privacy concerns, and the need for training and expertise to use AI effectively ([4](#), [10](#), [12](#), [13](#)).

Given the potential scale of use of AI, there is a need to regularly examine how AI-assisted interventions have been, are being, and could be used in public health contexts. To better understand and guide the potential use of AI in public health, we will conduct five linked reviews. The first three reviews will assess the effectiveness of AI-assisted interventions for reducing engagement with smoking, drinking alcohol, and physical inactivity. The fourth review will summarize current AI applications in health surveillance and policy decisions. **The fifth review will explore the potential role of AI in public health, including potential benefits and challenges.** To help maximise the utility of these reviews for a UK setting, only studies considering AI in high-income countries will be included. Additionally, all reviews will have a focus on health equity, particularly concerning inequities in access or use to AI-assisted interventions.

These reviews aim to inform public health professionals about the practical applications and most promising options for using AI in public health.

This protocol corresponds to the fifth review: the potential role of AI in public health.

2. Review Aim

The present reviews will systematically synthesise evidence from primary studies, reviews, opinion pieces, and editorials around the use of AI in public health in high-income countries to address the following question:

1. What is the potential role of AI in public health

3. Methods

This scoping review will be conducted with reference to the JBI updated methodological guidance for scoping reviews ([14](#)), and the protocol is reported with reference to JBI best practice guidance and reporting items for the development of scoping review protocols ([15](#)).

3.1. Patient and Public Involvement (PPI)

We will undertake a programme of patient and public involvement (PPI) with relevant stakeholder groups. There will be three phases of engagement ([Table 1](#)). First will be engagement in protocol refinement and confirmation, with a primary focus on specifying the inclusion criteria and clarifying the definition of key constructs related to: AI and its sub-domains; and the remit of public health that will be considered. Second will be engagement to provide feedback on preliminary and final synthesis findings. Third will be engagement on the development of implications for research, policy and practice.

We will undertake PPI with three UK wide communities of practice. Two of these communities are from NIHR funded research infrastructures:

- **NIHR Health Determinants Research Collaborations (HDRCs):** The NIHR has funded thirty HDRCs that aim to boot research capacity and capability within local government. They aim to embed a culture of using evidence in decision-making and to understand how decision impact on health and health inequalities. These

collaborations have the potential to use AI in their public health decision-making and practice.

- **NIHR Public Health Intervention Responsive Studies Teams (PHIRST):** Teams provide timely and accessible evaluations of public health interventions to Local Authorities. Evaluations have, or intend to, examine interventions that have used AI.
- **Local Government Association Artificial Intelligence Hub:** The hub comprises an AI network of over 300 office members that works to discuss AI risks, rewards and readiness in local government across the UK.

At each of these three phases we will host two online meetings, comprising a mixture of professionals from the three communities of practice. Combining professionals will hopefully spark dynamic and challenging discussion, while hosting two meetings will aim to maximise attendance.

3.2. Approach to Searching and Data Sources

One AI search facet will be used, which draws upon published and unpublished AI search filters either created by members of the InterTASC (Technology Appraisal Support Collaboration) Information Specialists' Sub-Group (ISSG) or hosted on the associated ISSG Search Filter Resource ([16](#)).

The search will combine the AI facet with public health terms and terms to capture papers discussing the future of AI in public health. These “future” terms have been derived from iterative searching, with pertinent words and MeSH terms harvested from relevant papers and reference lists. To this a systematic review filter ([17](#)) will be added. A second more focused search, without a study design filter, will be conducted and combined to ensure key editorials and opinion pieces are retrieved. A date limit from 01 January 2020 onwards will be used.

We will conduct searches in: Medline (Ovid); Embase (Ovid); Web of Science; and Scopus. Searches of Web of Science and Scopus will be undertaken to take advantage of their multi-disciplinary coverage, given the technological focus of the topic. Additionally, we will conduct supplementary literature searching as determined by the needs of each review, which may include checking reference lists, citation tracking, contacting authors, and web searching for unpublished material and policy documents.

The search strategy for Medline for is presented in [Supplement A](#).

3.3. Eligibility Criteria

The overall eligibility criteria are presented in [Table 2](#). These may be refined with stakeholders during the first phase of PPI.

Interventions must be AI tools that could be used in public health contexts in the future, including public health interventions, decision making, local disease modelling and prediction, or any other element of public health.

Included studies must be set in, or relevant to, high-income countries, as defined by the [World Bank](#). Included studies must also be in English language.

3.4. Study Screening Methods

Titles and abstracts from the search will be screened independently and in duplicate by two members of the review team. References included by at least one reviewer on eligibility assessment will progress to full-text screening.

Full texts of references will be independently screened by two reviewers. References identified through other means, such as reference checking and citation searching, will undergo duplicate title and abstract screening as above.

Conflicts in assessment will be resolved through discussion and recourse to a third member of the review team.

3.5. Software

Retrieved study reports from the data sources will be exported to Endnote 21, where they will be combined and de-duplicated. They will then be uploaded to Rayyan platform for title and abstract screening, and Microsoft Excel will be used for full text screening, data extraction, and quality appraisal (as necessary).

3.6. Quality Appraisal

The rationale for quality appraisal of study reports is to assess clarity and transparency of reporting; methodological rigour in the research process; robustness in the findings, including robustness in any claims to generalisability; and compliance with ethical standards. Nonetheless, we expect to include evidence from diverse studies, often without participants, where quality appraisal will likely be of limited use, and therefore will not conduct quality appraisal in this review.

3.7. Number of Reviewers

One member of the review team will lead information specialist activities related to study report retrieval (JK). Six members of the review team will undertake screening, extraction, and appraisal (SH; JK; RE; GMT; SL; RA). The remainder of the review team will serve as arbiters of decision conflicts in study screening, support the synthesis of findings, and develop the final funder recommendations.

3.8. Data Extraction and Coding

We will extract data for:

- Study identification: method of study identification; first author; publication year; title
- Public health context: area and context of AI use in public health activities
- Intervention: how AI could be used; context of AI usage; modality and type of AI; alternative to AI currently used; other relevant information about the use of AI
- Outcome data: anticipated benefits; anticipated challenges

Additional data in each review may be extracted depending on the needs of the review.

3.9. Synthesis

Broad summaries of how AI could be used in public health will be reported. The exact organisation of evidence will be determined once the studies have been identified and extracted, but will likely be structured by the type of intervention: public health interventions, decision making, local disease modelling and prediction, and any other element of public health. The anticipated benefits and challenges of using AI will be discussed.

We will highlight health equity considerations, with reference to PROGRESS-Plus characteristics (18). Specifically, we will report any findings from studies highlighting how use of AI could impact upon health equity.

3.10. Synthesis Output

Key characteristics of all included studies will be reported in summary tables. If possible, we will develop infographics to present the results of each review question. Finally, to support future intervention research and practice in this field, we will report on implications for research, policy, and practice.

3.11. Certainty of Evidence

We will not assess the certainty of evidence.

4. Ethics

Ethical approval for these reviews will not be required. PPI consultation with stakeholder groups will be conducted in accordance with any ethical requirements stipulated by the organisations and research studies that recruit participating members.

5. Discussion

This review will inform thinking around how AI could be best used in public health by summarising the potential, as well as the potential benefits and disadvantages, of using AI in public health contexts.

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Table 1. Stakeholder Engagement in Review Process

Review Stage	Stakeholder Groups	Identification of Stakeholders	Aims of Engagement
Development and confirmation of protocol	Two stakeholder groups. Each group to comprise 6 to 8 professionals from across the three communities of practice. Each group will aim to achieve representation from across the four nations.	<p>NIHR Health Determinants Research Collaborations (HDRCs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members of existing HDRCs from England, Scotland and Wales. <p>Northern Ireland does not currently have a funded HDRC.</p> <p>NIHR Public Health Intervention Responsive Studies Teams (PHIRST):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic members from the PHIRST teams across England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. Representatives from local authorities who have participated in PHIRST evaluations. <p>Local Government Association Artificial Intelligence Hub:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office members of the AI Intelligence hub. 	Refine inclusion criteria through definition of key concepts (for example, AI, public health).
Refinement and confirmation of preliminary and final findings	Two stakeholder groups. Each group to comprise 6 to 8 professionals from across the three communities of practice. Each group will aim to achieve representation from across the four nations.	<p>NIHR Health Determinants Research Collaborations (HDRCs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members of existing HDRCs from England, Scotland and Wales. <p>NIHR Public Health Intervention Responsive Studies Teams (PHIRST):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic members from the PHIRST teams across England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. Representatives from local authorities who have participated in PHIRST evaluations. <p>Local Government Association Artificial Intelligence Hub:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office members of the AI Intelligence hub. 	Provide feedback on preliminary findings. Refine and confirm final findings.
Development and confirmation of recommendations and dissemination strategy	Two stakeholder groups. Each group to comprise 6 to 8 professionals from across the three communities of practice. Each group will aim to achieve representation from across the four nations.	<p>NIHR Health Determinants Research Collaborations (HDRCs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members of existing HDRCs from England, Scotland and Wales. <p>NIHR Public Health Intervention Responsive Studies Teams (PHIRST):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic members from the PHIRST teams across England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. Representatives from local authorities who have participated in PHIRST evaluations. <p>Local Government Association Artificial Intelligence Hub:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office members of the AI Intelligence hub. 	<p>Generate implications for policy, practice and research.</p> <p>Refine and confirm dissemination strategy. Ensuring findings are accessible to intended audience.</p>

Table 2: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

	Included	Excluded
Population	Any	
Setting	High-income countries, as defined by the World Bank , or no specific country if applicable to high-income countries	Middle- and lower-income countries
Context	Any public health context	Pandemic, healthcare (including diagnostic), clinical, and other contexts
Intervention	<p>AI tools that could be used in public health contexts in the future, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • public health interventions • decision making • local disease modelling and prediction • any other element of public health <p>AI is broadly defined as algorithms integrated into systems and tools that can learn from data to be able to perform automated tasks without explicit human programming.</p>	Other interventions
Outcomes	The anticipated benefits and challenges of using AI in public health	Other outcomes
Language	English	Other languages
Date of publication	01 January 2020 to present	
Study design	Reviews (systematic, rapid, scoping, literature), opinion pieces, commentaries, editorials	Other study designs, including modelling studies
Publication type	Published or preprint	Conference abstracts

Supplement A: Search Strategy (Medline)

Database: Ovid MEDLINE(R) ALL (initial search dates [will be updated]: 1946 to July 15, 2025)

#	Query	Results
1	exp artificial intelligence/	243,836
2	exp Machine Learning/	98,411
3	(AI or AI4H).ti,ab.	76,708
4	("comput* intelligence" or "comput* reasoning" or "machine intelligence" or "artificial intelligence" or "natural language processing" or "llm*1 or "large language model*" or "language learning model*" or "classification algorithm*" or "computer heuristic*" or "convolutional network*" or DALL-E or "decision support system*" or "decision tree" or DeepAI or "deep learning" or "data science" or "feature detection" or "generative pre-trained transformer" or "generative pretrained transformer" or invideo or "learning algorithm*" or "machine learning" or "neural net*" or "reinforcement learning" or "learning algorithm*" or "*supervised learning" or "intelligent agent*").ti,ab,kf.	398,377
5	("boltzmann machine*" or "long short-term memory" or "gated recurrent unit*" or "rectified linear unit*" or autoencoder or "auto-encoder" or backpropagation or "multilayer perceptron" or "multi-layer perceptron" or convnet or "convolutional learning").ti,ab,kf.	21,765
6	("Bing chat" or ChatGPT* or "Chat GPT" or "Google* Bard" or "Google* Gemini" or "IBM Watson" or "Microsoft* Bing" or "Microsoft* Copilot" or OpenAI or "Open AI" or PathAI or "Path AI").ti,ab,kf.	7,628
7	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6	523,176
8	exp Public Health/	10,001,549
9	public health.ti,ab,kf.	449,029
10	exp Population Health/	41,443
11	"Social Determinants of Health"/	9,085
12	("population level" or "population health" or "determinants of health" or "health intelligence" or "health surveillance" or "health equity" or "health policy" or (health* adj2 promot*) or ((behavi?or or lifestyle*) adj2 (chang* or modif*))).ti,ab,kf.	283,564

13	epidemiolog*.ti,kw.	216,722
14	*Health Policy/	39,751
15	exp *Preventive Health Services/	378,371
16	8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15	10,498,671
17	Forecasting/	94,072
18	inventions/	3,460
19	exp "diffusion of innovation"/	22,225
20	(future or horizon or disrupt* or innovat* or forecasting or frontier* or nowcasting or trends or invention* or paradigm or "health 4.0").ti,kf.	411,338
21	(technolog* adj2 (new or novel or advances or innovat* or future or disrupt*)).ab.	85,848
22	17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21	572,419
23	7 and 16 and 22	6,182
24	(systematic review or meta-analysis).pt.	386,287
25	meta-analysis/ or systematic review/ or systematic reviews as topic/ or meta-analysis as topic/ or "meta analysis (topic)"/ or "systematic review (topic)"/ or exp technology assessment, biomedical/ or network meta-analysis/	432,838
26	((systematic* adj3 (review* or overview*)) or (methodologic* adj3 (review* or overview*))).ti,ab,kf.	428,385
27	((quantitative adj3 (review* or overview* or synthes*)) or (research adj3 (integrati* or overview*))).ti,ab,kf.	20,390
28	((integrative adj3 (review* or overview*)) or (collaborative adj3 (review* or overview*)) or (pool* adj3 analy*)).ti,ab,kf.	47,606
29	(data synthes* or data extraction* or data abstraction*).ti,ab,kf.	52,920
30	(handsearch* or hand search*).ti,ab,kf.	12,139
31	(mantel haenszel or peto or der simonian or dersimonian or fixed effect* or latin square*).ti,ab,kf.	42,083
32	(met analy* or metanaly* or technology assessment* or HTA or HTAs or technology overview* or technology appraisal*).ti,ab,kf.	14,347
33	(meta regression* or metaregression*).ti,ab,kf.	18,976
34	(meta-analy* or metaanaly* or systematic review* or biomedical technology assessment* or bio-medical technology assessment*).mp,hw.	588,145

35	(medline or cochrane or pubmed or medlars or embase or cinahl).ti,ab,hw.	440,447
36	(cochrane or (health adj2 technology assessment) or evidence report).jw.	22,884
37	(comparative adj3 (efficacy or effectiveness)).ti,ab,kf.	21,765
38	(outcomes research or relative effectiveness).ti,ab,kf.	12,469
39	((indirect or indirect treatment or mixed-treatment or bayesian) adj3 comparison*).ti,ab,kf.	5,092
40	(multi* adj3 treatment adj3 comparison*).ti,ab,kf.	338
41	(mixed adj3 treatment adj3 (meta-analy* or metaanaly*)).ti,ab,kf.	186
42	umbrella review*.ti,ab,kf.	2,893
43	(multi* adj2 paramet* adj2 evidence adj2 synthesis).ti,ab,kf.	15
44	(multiparamet* adj2 evidence adj2 synthesis).ti,ab,kf.	19
45	(multi-paramet* adj2 evidence adj2 synthesis).ti,ab,kf.	13
46	24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45	854,495
47	(review.pt. or (((integrated or integrative or narrative) adj (review or reviews)) or overview or ((state adj3 art) and (art adj (review or reviews)))).ti,ab,kf.) not (systematic or scoping).ti.	3,412,064
48	46 or 47	4,066,974
49	23 and 48	1,547
50	exp *Artificial Intelligence/es, hi, td [Ethics, History, Trends]	2,638
51	((future or horizon or disrupt* or innovat* or forecasting or frontier* or nowcasting or trends or invention* or paradigm or "health 4.0") and (AI or artificial intelligence)).ti.	2,549
52	50 or 51	4,976
53	Public health.ti,kf.	141,248
54	*artificial intelligence/ or *large language model/	34,790
55	(artificial intelligence or AI or llm* or machine learning or deep learning or expert system*).ti,kf.	196,106
56	54 or 55	210,509
57	53 and 56	1,004
58	49 or 52 or 57	7,247
59	limit 58 to yr="2020 -Current"	5,479